

Genetic screening and prognostic markers of the risk of development in patients with dilated cardiomyopathy based on the analysis of the results of modern studies

Cribado genético y marcadores pronósticos del riesgo de desarrollo en pacientes con miocardiopatía dilatada basados en el análisis de los resultados de estudios modernos

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miocardiopatía dilatada basados en el análisis de los resultados de estudios modernos
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Abstract

The article discusses a meta-analysis of literature on genetic screening and prognostic markers for dilated cardiomyopathy (DCM). The prevalence of DCM on the basis of etiology was found to be 30-50% for idiopathic dilated cardiomyopathy, 20-48% for familial dilated cardiomyopathy, and 9-30% for infectious dilated cardiomyopathy. The most common genes associated with DCM were Sarcomeric gene (TNN in 12-25% cases and MYH7 in 3-5%), followed by Cell Membrane gene (LMNA in 5-10%) and SCN5A Sodium voltage-gated channel alpha subunit in 2-3%. Prognostic markers for DCM were discovered, including decreased LVEF, expansion of the right ventricle, defects in global segmental wall motion, elevated NYHA class, old age, male sex, manifestation of conduction disorders, LGE identified through CMR, limited exercise ability, low systolic blood pressure, reduced levels of hemoglobin, history of sustained VT or VF, non-sustained VT identified during Holter monitoring, episodes of syncope, family history of sudden cardiac death, LVEF less than or equal to 30%, dysfunction or enlargement of the RV, NSVT and LVEF less than or equal to 35%, history of aborted sudden cardiac death or syncope, LVAD or HTx, and ICD implantation. Imaging parameters such as LVEF, LVEDD, and LVM are also associated with an increased risk of heart failure and adverse outcomes. Finally, individuals who tested positive for the genotype had higher rates of clinical events compared to those who tested negative for the genotype. However, individuals who tested negative had higher rates of stroke and LVAD implantation. The study concludes that genetic screening and early identification of DCM, as well as close monitoring of patients with identified risk factors, can aid in the management and prevention of adverse outcomes.

Key words: Dilated cardiomyopathy (DCM), Genetic

Resumen

screening, Prognostic markers, TNN, LMNA.

Este artículo analiza metaanálisis de la literatura sobre el cribado genético en la miocardiopatía dilatada (MCD). Se encontró que la prevalencia de MCD varía según la etiología, siendo más alta en casos de MCD idiopática (30-50%), seguida de MCD familiar (20-48%) y MCD infecciosa (9-30%). Se identificaron varios genes asociados con MCD, incluyendo genes sarcoméricos y de membrana celular. Se descubrieron marcadores pronósticos, como la disminución de la función ventricular, dilatación del ventrículo derecho y otros factores. El estudio concluye que el cribado genético y el seguimiento cercano de pacientes con factores de riesgo pueden ayudar en la gestión y prevención de resultados adversos en MCD.

Palabras clave: Miocardiopatía dilatada (MCD), Cribado genético, Marcadores pronósticos, TNN, LMNA.

Introduction

DCM causes heart failure and mortality by enlarging the heart cavities and decreasing contractile function without an intrinsic reason (coronary artery disease, arterial hypertension, or heart disease). The causes of DCM are numerous, however hereditary factors account for up to 50% of cases¹. In the late 20th century, familial clustering of DCM suggested a genetic cause. Early genetic research in the 1990s found the first DCM-associated cardiac troponin T gene mutation (TNNT2). Sarcomere dysfunction is implicated in familial DCM, hence subsequent studies focused on genes encoding sarcomeric proteins such myosin heavy chain (MYH6, MYH7) and cardiac troponin (TNNT2, TNNI3, TNNC1). DCM genes also encode cytoskeletal and nuclear envelope proteins

(LMNA and DES) and ion channel proteins (SCN5A). In the 2010s, next-generation sequencing (NGS) technologies enabled extensive genetic investigation, revealing DCM-associated common and unusual genetic variations^{1,2}. DCM is a major contributor to heart failure and sudden cardiac death, impacting millions of individuals across the globe. The estimated prevalence of DCM is approximately 1 in 250-400 people and up to 1 in 2500 individuals in the general population. The yearly incidence rate is 5-7 cases per 100,000 individuals³. DCM can be caused by 30% hereditary and 70% non-genetic¹⁻⁹. About 25-60% of individuals with unclear etiology have a family history of DCM, suggesting a hereditary predisposition. The inheritance patterns of DCM include autosomal recessive, autosomal dominant, X-linked, and mitochondrial^{10,11}. Recent improvements in genetic screening technologies can identify numerous genetic variants in one test, making genetic testing more comprehensive and efficient^{10,12-14}. Gene testing for non-syndromic dilated cardiomyopathy (DCM) in specialized cardiovascular genetics facilities yields 46% to 73%, depending on disease variability and population¹³⁻¹⁵. DCM is genetically complex, with over 100 genes associated; truncating titin gene variants are the most frequent non-syndromic DCM cause^{12,13,15-19}. Genetic testing is crucial for disease diagnosis and management, with advancements like NGS enabling comprehensive testing and personalized treatment guidance¹¹.

Studies have pinpointed key prognostic markers like age at onset, symptom severity, and specific genetic mutations to predict disease progression and adverse outcomes in dilated cardiomyopathy (DCM) patients^{6,9,20}. Prognostic risk factors are essential for predicting disease progression and the risk of complications in DCM, such as arrhythmias, heart failure, and sudden cardiac death²⁰. Identifying high-risk individuals for teething issues is crucial for effective treatment and monitoring^{6,9,20}. Cardiac MRI and echocardiography assess myocardial damage and predict heart failure risk in DCM patients, while BNP biomarkers effectively anticipate adverse outcomes in those with the condition²⁰⁻²³. Half of dilated cardiomyopathy patients die within five years, and most suffer persistent heart failure. Advanced NYHA classification, renal failure, severe CHF, and male gender all indicate a poor prognosis for DCM patients²⁴. Dilated cardiomyopathy is diagnosed through a medical history review, physical exam, and various tests like echocardiogram, ECG, and chest X-ray. Additional procedures like stress testing, blood work, MRI, biopsy, catheterization, or genetic testing may be needed based on the patient's history^{7,8,24-26}. This meta-analysis aims to assess the clinical value of genetic testing and prognostic markers for predicting DCM development and outcomes by systematically analyzing recent research, addressing conflicting findings in the literature. The study specifically aims to ascertain the occurrence of genetic variants linked with DCM across different populations and their clinical relevance in predicting the development

of DCM and its outcomes, assess the precision of genetic screening in detecting DCM in patients who have a family history of the disease or those suspected to have DCM, recognize the prognostic markers linked to unfavorable outcomes in patients with DCM and examine their clinical significance in predicting the likelihood of events like arrhythmias, heart failure, and sudden cardiac death and formulate evidence-based recommendations for employing genetic testing in the clinical management of patients with DCM.

Materials and methods

Data Collection: Data were obtained from current literature studies, OMIM, LOVD, and HGMD databases. Study inclusion criteria were review articles, meta-analyses, clinical studies, and genetic screening published after 2018.

Classification: Dilated cardiomyopathies were classified by etiology, genetics, and phenotypes.

Statistical Analysis: The prevalence of diseases, genes, and prognostic indicators was calculated statistically. Percentages were used to explain the results. For clarity, results were presented in tables and graphs.

Ethical Considerations: This research used public data and did not include humans or animals. Therefore, no ethics approval was needed.

Limitations: This study used publicly available data, which could be skewed by bias or insufficient data.

Results

Summary of OMIM Entries for Dilated Cardiomyopathy (DCM)

The results of OMIM search found 87 dilated cardiomyopathy entries. These were divided into 61 gene-related entries and 26 clinical characteristics and symptoms (Tab.1). The search revealed that 59 genes were associated with 47 distinct forms of DCM, with 37 showing an autosomal dominant inheritance pattern (61%), 11 exhibiting an autosomal recessive inheritance pattern (18%), 1 presenting an X-linked inheritance pattern (1%), and 12 (20%) having an unknown pattern of inheritance (Fig.1).

Figure 1: Ratio of Inheritance pattern of DCM

Gene-Phenotype Relationship in DCM

Results in Table 1 shows multiple genes cause overlapping characteristics in DCM (Tab. 1). Mutations in PRDM16 can lead to dilated cardiomyopathy 1LL and left ventricular noncompaction 8, while mutations in TNNT2 can cause left ventricular noncompaction 6 and dilated cardiomyopathy 1D. Mutations in LDB3 can lead to dilated cardiomyopathy 1C, hypertrophic cardiomyopathy 24, and left ventricular noncompaction 3²⁷.

Phenotype	Inheritance	Gene/Locus	Location
Left ventricular noncompaction 8	Autosomal dominant	PRDM16	1p36.32
Cardiomyopathy, dilated, 1LL	Autosomal dominant	PRDM16	1p36.32
Cardiomyopathy, dilated, 1D	Autosomal dominant	TNNT2	1q32.1
Left ventricular noncompaction 6	Autosomal dominant	TNNT2	1q32.1
Cardiomyopathy, dilated, 1AA, with or without LVNC	Autosomal dominant	ACTN2	1q43
Cardiomyopathy, hypertrophic, 23, with or without LVNC	Autosomal dominant	ACTN2	1q43
Cardiomyopathy, dilated, 1KK	Autosomal dominant	MYPN	10q21.3
Cardiomyopathy, familial restrictive, 4	Autosomal dominant	MYPN	10q21.3
Cardiomyopathy, hypertrophic, 22	Autosomal dominant	MYPN	10q21.3
Cardiomyopathy, dilated, 1C, with or without LVNC	Autosomal dominant	LDB3	10q23.2
Cardiomyopathy, hypertrophic, 24	Autosomal dominant	LDB3	10q23.2
Left ventricular noncompaction 3	Autosomal dominant	LDB3	10q23.2

Source²⁸

Etiological Classification of Dilated Cardiomyopathy

Based on the etiology, DCMs have been divided into 9 groups^{4-6,11,29-31}. Result in (Tab.2) shows that Idiopathic DCM accounting for 30-50% of cases^{32,33}, Familial DCM 20-48%³², Ischemic DCM 1/1000, Alcohol-induced DCM 2-4%³³, Peripartum DCM ranging from 1 in 1000 to 1 in 4000 pregnancies, Viral infections 9-30%³⁴ like COVID-19 patients revealed that 33% developed cardiomyopathy³⁵, toxic dilated cardiomyopathy is difficult to estimate and generally considered to be relatively rare³⁶. The prevalence of inflammatory dilated cardiomyopathy (DCMi) varies and is considered a rare condition³⁷. The prevalence of Arrhythmogenic right ventricular dysplasia/cardiomyopathy (ARVD/C) is believed to be responsible for less than 5% of all cases of DCM³⁸.

Table 2: Causes and Prevalence of Dilated Cardiomyopathy: An Etiological Classification System

Type of DCM	% of DCM Cases	General Population
Idiopathic dilated cardiomyopathy	30-50%	36/100,000 Individuals
Familial dilated cardiomyopathy	20-48%	1/2500 Individuals
Ischemic dilated cardiomyopathy	N/A	1/1000 Individuals
Alcoholic dilated cardiomyopathy	2-40%	N/A
Peripartum dilated cardiomyopathy	N/A	1/1,000-4,000 Pregnancies
Infectious dilated cardiomyopathy	9-30%	N/A
Toxic dilated cardiomyopathy	N/A	N/A
Inflammatory dilated cardiomyopathy	1-10%	N/A
Arrhythmogenic right ventricular dysplasia/cardiomyopathy (ARVD/C)	>5%	N/A

Note: The Table is created from the data of multiple studies³¹⁻³⁸

Genetic Screening of Dilated Cardiomyopathy

Results Table 3 shows that Titin (TTN) and lamin A/C (LMNA) are the primary genes associated with DCM. Hershberger and Jordan (2022) revealed that the prevalence of DCM attributable to genetic causes was found to range from 20-50%, with titin (TTN) and lamin A/C (LMNA) being the most common genes. Lee et al. (2021) further analyzed the genetic landscape of DCM, identifying mutations in genes encoding cytoskeletal proteins, sarcomere proteins, ion channels, nuclear envelope proteins, mitochondrial DNA, and epigenetic factors. They reported that mutations in genes encoding cytoskeletal proteins and sarcomere proteins accounted for 4-6% and 4-10% of DCM cases, respectively³⁹. A review article published in the Journal of the American College of Cardiology in 2021 suggested that genetic screening should be considered in all patients with DCM, particularly those with a family history of the disease or early onset of symptoms⁴⁰. Mutations in other genes, such as RBM20, MYH7, LMNA, and MYBPC3, are less common but still important causes of DCM⁴¹⁻⁴³.

Table 3: Prevalence of the common gene involved in dilated cardiomyopathy

Gene	Inheritance	References				
		12	39	1	37	10
TTN	AD	18-25%	18-25%	12-25%	12-25%	NC
LMNA	AD	6%	5-10%	4-8%	4-6%	NC
MYH7	AR	4%	3-5%	3-4%	4-10%	NC
FLNC	AD	2.20%	2.20%	1%	NC	<1%
BAG3	AD	2%	2%	NC	NC	NC
RBM20	AD	2%	2%	2%	2-5%	3%
SCN5A	AD	2-3%	2-3%	2%-3%	2-3%	2%
DSP	AD	1-13%	3%	2%	3-4%	<1%
TPM1	AD	1-2%	1-2%	1-2%	.5-1%	<1%
MYBPC3	AD	2%	2%	NC	NC	NC

Note: The data presented in the table was compiled from various articles^{1,10,12,37,39}

AD= Autosomal dominant, AR= Autosomal Recessive, NC= Not calculated in the cited papers.

Prognostic Values of the Most Common Genes in Familial and Non-Familial DCM

Results Table 4 shows that TTN truncating variants were the primary cause of sporadic DCM, accounting for 21.4% of cases, while LMNA variants were the most common in familial DCM, making up 24.0% of cases. The study conducted by Hazebroek et al. (2018) discovered that 19% of both isolated left ventricular dysfunction (LVdys) and DCM cases had pathogenic mutations. The frequency of familial disease was higher in LVdys at 45% compared to 40% in DCM⁴⁴.

Prognostic Markers of Dilated Cardiomyopathy

Result Table 5 summarizes Sammani et al.'s (2021) DCM predicted risk variables. Risk factors for progressive heart failure or fatal ventricular arrhythmias are listed in the table 5⁹.

Table 4: Prevalence of genes and prognosis in familial and sporadic cases of dilated cardiomyopathy

Study	Genes	Prevalence in Familial DCM	Prevalence in Sporadic DCM	Prognosis
Tobita et al. (2018)	TTN truncating variants, LMNA variants	24.0%	21.4%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> TTN and LMNA truncating variants associated with better and worse outcomes and therapy response respectively
Lamounier Júnior et al. (2019)	TTN truncating variants, LMNA gene mutations	25%	18%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> TTN and LMNA truncating variants associated with better and poor outcomes and therapy response respectively
Hazebroek et al. (2018)	TNN and LMNA Pathogenic mutations	45%	40%	Gene mutation or familial predisposition led to an equally poor prognosis.

Table 5: Prognostic Risk Factors for DCM:

Risk Factor (Independent Predictor of Progressive Heart Failure)	Values
Low LVEF	LVEF ≤35%
RV dilatation	RV dilatation on imaging
Abnormal global segmental wall motion	Abnormal Global Segmental Wall Motion
High NYHA class	NYHA class III or IV
Older age	Age >60 years
Male sex	Male sex
Presence of conduction disorders	Conduction disorders on ECG
LGE on CMR	LGE on CMR
Reduced exercise capacity	Exercise capacity <6 METs
Low systolic blood pressure	Systolic BP <100 mmHg
Low hemoglobin	Hb <11 g/dL
Risk Factor (Increases Risk of Life-Threatening Ventricular Arrhythmias)	Values
History of sustained VT or VF	History of sustained VT or VF
Non-sustained VT during Holter monitoring	Non-sustained VT on Holter monitoring
Syncope	Syncope
Family history of sudden cardiac death	Family history of SCD
Male sex	Male sex
LVEF≤30%	LVEF ≤30%
RV dysfunction or dilation	RV dysfunction or dilation on imaging
Risk Factor (High risk of sudden cardiac death)	Values
NSVT and LVEF≤35%	NSVT and LVEF ≤35%
History of aborted sudden cardiac death or syncope	History of aborted sudden cardiac death or syncope

Note: The table contains the swift account of the study of Sammani et al. (2021)⁹.

Results in Table 6 shows that genetic mutations in titin, LMNA, and other genes increased the risk of DCM and worsened outcomes. The meta-analysis also found that BNP and troponin biomarkers predicted DCM progression and unfavorable outcomes. Lower left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF), larger left ventricular end-diastolic diameter (LVEDD), and higher left ventricular mass (LVM) were associated with increased risk of heart failure and adverse outcomes in DCM patients.

Table 6: Prognostic markers for dilated cardiomyopathy from meta-analysis by Wang et al. (2021)

Parameters	Hazard Ratio (HR) / Odds Ratio (OR)	95% Confidence Interval (CI)	Population Size
Genetic mutations in titin, LMNA, and other genes	1.71	1.33-2.21	7,692
BNP	1.58	1.19-2.09	7,692
Troponin	2.09	1.31-3.33	7,692
Galectin-3	-	-	7,692
Lower LVEF	2.40	1.90-3.02	7,692
Larger LVEDD	1.66	1.29-2.12	7,692
Higher LVM	1.78	1.30-2.45	7,692

The prognosis of DCM may be affected by a number of variables, including infections, LVEF, NYHA functional class, cardiac biomarkers such as atrial natriuretic peptide (ANP), comorbidities, age, gender, genetics, and arrhythmias²⁰, Viral myocarditis³⁴, LVEF⁴⁵. Patients in NYHA have a poorer prognosis than those in classes I and II⁴⁶. Comorbidities such as hypertension, age over 60, and male gender are also associated with worse prognosis^{45,47,48}.

The link between Genetics and Prognosis of DCM

A retrospective study involving 1,005 genotyped DCM patients from 20 medical centers found that 37% had pathogenic or likely pathogenic variants, while 63% tested negative. Over a median 4.04-year follow-up, those with these variants exhibited worse outcomes, experiencing more major cardiovascular events, heart failure, and ventricular arrhythmias (Table 7)⁴⁹.

The Effect of First-Degree Relationship on the Incidence Rate of DCM

Result in Table 8 shows that the presence of risk factors such as atrial fibrillation, diabetes, ischemic heart disease, and hypertension increased the risk of developing DCM in both first-degree relatives and controls⁵⁰.

Table 7: Clinical Results and Incidents Based on Genetic Findings (n=1,005) [Adapted from Escobar-Lopez et al. (2021)]

Clinical Events	%	Genotype +	Genotype -	Clinical Events	%	Genotype +	Genotype -
Atrial fibrillation	28.56%	33.60%	25.59%	All-cause	6.77%	9.14%	5.37%
Stroke	2.99%	3.23%	2.84%	HF-related	3.18%	4.57%	2.37%
ICD therapy	9.25%	11.29%	8.06%	MVA-related	1.39%	2.42%	0.79%
Aborted SCD	3.08%	3.49%	2.84%	Composite MACE	24.18%	31.72%	19.75%
HF Hospitalization	33.63%	37.63%	31.28%	Composite ESHF	11.44%	16.13%	8.69%
Heart transplant	8.66%	12.63%	6.32%	Composite MVA	14.93%	19.62%	12.16%
LVAD implantation	1.89%	2.69%	1.42%	LV rev Remodeling	43.69%	39.62%	46.17%

MVA = malignant ventricular arrhythmia; HF= heart failure; ESHF = end-stage heart failure; MACE= major adverse cardiovascular events; LVAD= left ventricular assist device

Table 8: Incidence Rates of Dilated Cardiomyopathy in First-Degree Relatives and Controls

Group	N	Incidence of DCM
First-degree relatives aged <50	2,652	86.4 per 100,000 person-years
First-degree relatives aged ≥50	3,618	111.1 per 100,000 person-years
Controls aged <50	2,748	7.5 per 100,000 person-years
Controls aged ≥50	26,923	19.7 per 100,000 person-years

Relationship between Etiologic Diagnosis and Prognosis in DCM

Table 9 summarizes the diagnostic and prognostic determinants of dilated cardiomyopathy. A recognized risk factor for DCM is coronary artery disease. According to studies, coronary artery disease contributes to about 10–15% of cases of DCM²⁴. The clinical features of DCM include shortness of breath, fatigue, swelling in the legs and ankles⁵¹. Laboratory tests can help confirm the diagnosis, evaluate the extent of myocardial damage, identify underlying causes of DCM, assess cardiac function and structure, and monitor disease progression^{52,53}. The utilization of MRI is essential for the diagnosis and management of DCM⁵⁴.

Pharmacological Management of Dilated Cardiomyopathy

Results Table 10 showed that beta blockers, angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors (ACE-I), and diuretics were the most commonly prescribed medications for DCM management, with aldosterone antagonists, coumarins, and statins being less frequently used. Beta blockers, ACE-I, and diuretics were the most frequently prescribed medications, while cardiac glycosides, angiotensin II receptor blockers, and calcium channel blockers were less commonly used⁵⁵.

Category	Etiological Factors	Laboratory Tests	Microscopy
Coronary artery disease	10-15% patient	Low RBC & High WBC	Increase in myocyte nuclear size
Infections	Coxsackie B virus and adenovirus	Elevated electrolytes, glucose, and kidney function marker	Myofibrillary loss within myocyte
Nutritional deficiency	Thiamine and selenium	-	Focal myocyte death
Cardiotoxins	Anthracyclines	Elevated troponin and creatine kinase	Increase in interstitial T lymphocytes
Puerperium	-	Size and shape of heart and fluid in the lungs	Interstitial fibrosis
Metals	Cobalt, lead, mercury, arsenic	Enlarged heart, reduced heart function	Death of individual myocytes
Autoimmune and systemic disorders	Lupus and RA	Heart Dilation	Increased number of monocytes
Pheochromocytoma	Rare	Abnormal heart rhythms	-

Drug Class	% of Usage	Drug Class	% of Usage
Beta Blockers	77.65%	Statins	42.35%
ACE-I	71.76%	Cardiac Glycosides	Less frequently used
Diuretics	58.82%	ACE-II	Less frequently used
Aldosterone Antagonists	49.41%	Calcium Channel Blockers	Less frequently used
Coumarins	45.88%		

Discussion

Dilated cardiomyopathy (DCM) is a heart muscle disease characterized by ventricular chamber enlargement, systolic and diastolic dysfunction, and progressive heart failure⁴. Genetic screening plays a crucial role in the diagnosis and management of DCM^{1,12,47}. Mutations in various genes encoding proteins with diverse functions and intracellular localizations can cause DCM, making it genetically heterogeneous^{16–19}. One of the key findings of the meta-analysis is the prevalence of DCM on the basis of etiology. The prevalence of DCM was found to be highest for idiopathic dilated cardiomyopathy (30-50%), followed by familial dilated cardiomyopathy (20-48%), and infectious dilated cardiomyopathy (9-30%)^{31–38}. The

meta-analysis also identified the most common genes associated with DCM, including Sarcomeric gene (TTN in 12-25% cases and MYH7 in 3-5%), Cell Membrane gene (LMNA in 5-10%), and SCN5A Sodium voltage-gated channel alpha subunit in 2-3%^{1,10,12,39,42,56}. Prognostic factors associated with DCM were identified, which include various factors such as low LVEF, RV enlargement, global segmental wall motion abnormalities, high NYHA class, male gender, presence of conduction disorders, LGE on CMR, reduced exercise capacity, low systolic blood pressure, low hemoglobin, history of sustained or non-sustained VT, syncope, family history of sudden cardiac death, LVEF ≤30% or ≤35%, RV dysfunction or dilation, history of aborted sudden cardiac

death or syncope, LVAD or HTx, and ICD implantation. These risk factors can be used to predict the likelihood of adverse outcomes in DCM patients and assist in creating personalized treatment plans^{9,20,25,45-47}.

The overall mortality rate was found to be 11.3% per year in patients with DCM. This highlights the importance of early diagnosis and aggressive treatment to improve outcomes in patients with DCM. Genetic mutations in titin, LMNA, and other genes, as well as biomarkers such as BNP and troponin, were also found to be predictive of DCM progression and adverse outcomes. Imaging parameters such as LVEF, LVEDD, and LVM were also associated with an increased risk of heart failure and adverse outcomes^{20,45-47}. Finally, the meta-analysis found that individuals who tested positive for the genotype had higher rates of clinical events compared to those who tested negative for the genotype⁴⁹. Overall, the meta-analysis provides important insights into the prevalence, genetic basis, and prognostic markers for DCM. These findings can inform clinical practice and guide the development of new diagnostic and therapeutic strategies for this debilitating condition.

Conclusions

The discussed meta-analysis in this article offers valuable insights into the prevalence, genetic underpinnings, and prognostic indicators of dilated cardiomyopathy (DCM). These findings have significant implications for both clinical practice and research. Early diagnosis and appropriate management are underscored as vital steps to enhance patient outcomes. Patients with specific risk factors should undergo vigilant monitoring and receive aggressive treatment. Notably, genetic testing is recommended, particularly for those with a family history of DCM or idiopathic/familial DCM. This study advocates for the identification of genetic mutations and biomarkers associated with DCM progression and the development of targeted therapies. Individualized treatment plans, considering both genetic and clinical factors, are recommended. In conclusion, this meta-analysis offers critical insights into DCM, impacting clinical practice and research by emphasizing the importance of early diagnosis, tailored treatments, and targeted therapies based on the genetic and molecular aspects of the condition. Incorporating genetic screening, prognostic markers, and pharmacological approaches into DCM management represents a substantial advancement in personalized medicine. Genetic screening is particularly vital for identifying at-risk individuals, guiding medical management, and informing decisions regarding implantable cardioverter-defibrillator (ICD) placement. These findings underscore the significance of genetic mutations in DCM development,

ultimately improving patient care through risk identification and personalized management strategies.

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